

Risk Response Actions in the preparation of Undergraduate Final Project Reports – UFPR (Undergraduate Thesis) when using Project-Based Learning

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Abstract

Project-based learning (PBL) has gained increasing prominence in engineering education because it enriches students' professional knowledge. Despite the growing interest in implementing PBL in engineering education, a comprehensive literature review has identified a significant gap: specific studies addressing risk response actions in preparing undergraduate theses using PBL have not been found. A paper titled "Proposal of Method for Risk Assessment of Failure in Undergraduate Final Project Report – UFPR (Undergraduate Thesis) when using Project-Based Learning" was presented at the PAEE/ALE'2023 international conference on active learning in engineering education. However, the study did not present the required response actions for identified risks. This study introduces guidance with risk response actions to manage the adequate preparation of undergraduate theses in engineering. A case study focused on resolving real-world problems local companies face within a specific region, with PBL as a supporting framework. This case study complements the findings presented at PAEE/ALE'2023 with tables outlining detailed actions to be taken during different processes to mitigate risks and prevent failure. The study concludes that the proposed actions can potentially optimize resources and, consequently, enhance the overall quality of undergraduate theses. Furthermore, this research lays the groundwork for future endeavors in engineering education, providing a framework to streamline and enhance the undergraduate thesis experience for students, professors, and decision-makers involved in thesis supervision.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Project-Based Learning - PBL; Undergraduate Thesis

1 Introduction

In engineering education, student-centered teaching methods, mainly Project-Based Learning (PBL), have gained widespread adoption. Despite its popularity, universities often grapple with unforeseen challenges while implementing PBL and may revert to conventional teaching approaches (Henderson, 2012). Hence, it becomes imperative to identify, articulate, and address risk factors directly influencing the preparation of undergraduate theses. Notably, the existing literature in engineering education has shown a deficiency in addressing the risks associated with undergraduate thesis failure, with even less attention given to risk responses. In response to this gap, the authors conducted a literature review to pinpoint key risk factors in preparing undergraduate theses. Recognizing these risks and understanding how to respond effectively can enhance success rates and establish a sustainable teaching methodology within universities. Current studies on the use of PBL in higher education are the one by Kaedi et al. (2023), which compared the effectiveness of problem-based learning (PBL) and lecture-based learning (LBL) methods to teaching research methods by mixed-methods approach in an explanatory sequential design. Lin et al. (2023) studied the PBL teaching method. They explored the new trend of reforming teaching thinking, teaching mode, and teaching means of the introductory courses of engineering majors to cultivate students' innovative thinking and improve their innovative ability. Para-González et al. (2023) empirically examined whether PBL improves apprenticeship abilities' development and promotes Students' subject overcoming and their Professional success using data from 65 Spanish University students. Leatemia et al. 's (2023) study aimed to identify teacher profiles that would

reveal teachers' specific educational needs and investigate the relationship between these profiles and the PBL training previously received. However, a gap exists in understanding how PBL influences the quality and effectiveness of final project reports, a crucial component of undergraduate research. The study contributes to the literature by assessing the risks associated with the preparation of undergraduate thesis preparation in engineering education. The diversity of identified risk factors underscores the intricacy of the process. Addressing most of these risks necessitates appropriate responses, justifying the need for the proposed study. Projects may falter without identifying and adequately mitigating risks, depriving students, professors, and partner organizations of anticipated benefits. The proposed method can potentially enhance professors' and students' skills and practices, ultimately elevating the quality of undergraduate theses. It is crucial to note that the study focuses explicitly on PBL, which involves collaboration with external companies. Completing undergraduate thesis projects can significantly mitigate business risks and improve quality and organizational safety. The existing literature review revealed a lack of studies comprehensively addressing risk assessment and its impacts on undergraduate theses. This study identifies risks and proposes a method to address them. The research questions guiding this study revolve around:

- 1 – What are the risks factors and actions to avoid or mitigate risks in PBL conducted in local companies during undergraduate thesis preparation?
- 2 – How can professors and students manage undergraduate thesis processes digitally and applying different learning theories?

The paper is organized into five sections: the first introduces the context and problem, the second presents studies about PBL in Undergraduate Final Projects. The third the Theoretical Learning theories applied in Undergraduate Final. Section 4 outlines the methodology, Section 5 presents the results, Section 6 discusses the results, and Section 7 concludes the study.

2 The PBL in Undergraduate Final Projects

Studies about PBL highlight its effectiveness in promoting active learning, critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and other skills essential for academic, professional, and personal success. The importance of PBL is recognized in various educational settings to prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century. Previous significant studies about PBL are presented herein. Palmer and W. Hall (2011) presented a PBL offering in engineering at Griffith University in Australia, observing that students generally enjoyed the experience, with aspects needing improvement listed and documented. Du et al. (2013) developed a framework of change in educational culture for sustainability using a PBL methodology, inspiring curriculum design for sustainability education. García-Martín and Pérez-Martínez (2017) presented a method to guide teachers using PBL principles and instructional design models, focusing on fundamental issues in active learning. Marques (2018) proposed a formative monitoring method to enhance students' individual and team performance, with results indicating that PBL effectively enhanced the learning experience. Setiawan (2019) conducted a study on implementing PBL, explicitly focusing on opportunities and challenges, where students chose their topics and explained their problem-solving approaches. Moliner et al. (2019) described the experience of using PBL in Materials Science courses conducted by Spanish universities, analyzing the perceptions of students and lecturers in the PBL process. Schneider (2020) used PBL to enhance student engagement. Daun (2016) discussed results from the application of such a course design in a graduate setting, indicating that PBL techniques foster different teaching goals in graduate and undergraduate settings. The study by Bhaskar et al. (2023) has identified and prioritized four main inhibiting factors. Institutional-level factors have secured the highest rank, followed by technological, operational, and personal-level factors. Merola et al. 's (2022) study explores how international student satisfaction is affected by some aspects of the learning and experience. Nguyen et al. (2022) provided

a conceptual structure and charted the evolution of human resource management research in higher education from 1966 to 2019. Sousa et al. (2022) analyzed the organizational culture of two higher education institutions, one from Portugal and another from Spain. Previous studies show that PBL is a teaching method involving students investigating and solving complex, real-world problems. Various factors can influence the design of PBL, and educators need to consider these factors to create effective and engaging learning experiences. By carefully considering these factors, educators can create PBL experiences that are engaging, meaningful, and aligned with educational objectives. The flexibility of the PBL method allows for customization to suit the unique needs of students and the learning environment. Pereira et al (2022) stated that PBL projects conducted in collaboration with local companies involve students working on real-world problems and applying theoretical knowledge to practical situations.

3 Theoretical Learning theories applied in Undergraduate Final Projects

Final project reports play a crucial role in undergraduate education by providing students with valuable research experience, developing essential skills, and preparing them for future academic and professional pursuits. Additionally, they benefit educational institutions by promoting deeper learning, assessing student learning outcomes, and fostering a research culture. Haritha and Rao (2024) present the theory on experiential learning and Kolb's Experiential Learning Cycle, which emphasizes the importance of the learning cycle - concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Final project reports can provide a platform for students to reflect on their experiences, develop abstract concepts from their research, and plan future actions based on their findings. Rohman et al. (2024) studied Piaget's Theory of Cognitive Development, which suggests that learners actively construct their understanding through interaction with experiences and the environment. Final project reports allow students to solidify their knowledge by organizing their research findings and constructing a coherent argument. Ott (2024) describes Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which highlights the importance of self-efficacy in learning. Final project reports can foster self-directed learning by requiring students to take ownership of their research process, make independent decisions, and manage their time effectively. Rosser and Sole (2024) studied the Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking proposed by Schön's Reflective Practice, which emphasizes the importance of reflection in professional practice. Final project reports encourage students to critically evaluate their research process, identify challenges, and propose solutions. Ilhami (2024) studied Bloom's Taxonomy, which categorizes learning objectives. Final project reports serve as a cornerstone of a well-rounded undergraduate education. By offering students a platform for experiential learning (Haritha & Rao, 2024), knowledge solidification (Rohman et al., 2024), and self-directed learning (Ott, 2024), these projects equip graduates with the research skills and critical thinking necessary for future success. Furthermore, final project reports benefit institutions by fostering a research culture (Rosser & Sole, 2024) and providing a comprehensive assessment tool that aligns with Bloom's Taxonomy (Ilhami, 2024). Ultimately, final project reports represent a valuable bridge between theory and practice, preparing students for lifelong learning and professional endeavors.

4 Methodology

The study adopted the approach of building theory from Case Study Research proposed by Eisenhardt (1989), and Yin, R. (2014). It combined data from archives, interviews, and observations in conducting PBL projects.

4.1 Population and Sample

The sample for the study was the PBL process utilized in the engineering course from the population of courses of a specific university. The number of stakeholders participating in the study is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Stakeholders

Area	Function	Number of Participants	Average time of experience (years)
University	Engineering Students	3	4
	PBL leader focal point	1	20
Company	Employee member of PBL	1	25
University	Professors	2	10

These stakeholders were selected based on their expertise. The sample size is appropriate and significant since all the interested parties are covered.

4.2 Instruments and Tools

A process map was created to comprehend the variables involved, and a face-to-face interview was conducted to pinpoint details of the processes and the potential risks in each step.

4.3 Data Collection

Data were collected from archives, interviews, and observations during the process. Risk factors were compiled by referencing existing literature and the process map. Participants, including students, professors, and organizational leaders, were surveyed to ascertain the probabilities associated with these risk factors.

4.4 Data Analysis & Actions

Ultimately, risk responses were formulated to address those risks identified by participants.

5 Results

This section shows the chart with the process groups involved in the Undergraduate Final Project Reports preparation, details of each process, the risks, the actions to mitigate or avoid the risks, and the proposed digital process to manage the processes presented in the chart with the process's groups.

5.1 Processes Groups

The Processes Groups involved in preparing the Undergraduate Final Project Reports are presented in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the processes in each phase of the report development. The GFRP Charter is prepared in the initiation phase, and stakeholders are identified. In Phase 2, the Planning (GFRP Plan) is prepared, starting with the scope (collect requirements, define the scope, and create WBS), then the schedule preparation (definition of actions, sequencing, and duration of activities), the definition of stakeholders (define stakeholder management plan), Quality plan (Define Quality requirements), Communication plan (Define communication plan) and finally the Risks identification (Plan, identify, analyze, define risk responses). Phase 3 is the Execution Phase, with the collection and distribution of information, management stakeholders, and the management of Schedule and Quality. In Phase 4, the monitoring and control happen, with the control of scope, risk, quality, schedule, and stakeholders. In Phase 5, the finalization of the GFRP, with the technical solution, preparation of the final GFRP, and paper. The Evaluation happens in three Steps. The first one is the Preparation of the GFR Plan; the second is the intermediate Evaluation with the presentation of GFRP by the student to the mentor professor and the Final Evaluation, with the course completion work (GFRP report) presentation to the examining board. The process must be documented in an electronic format, such as Google Form or another similar one.

Figure 1. Process Management Groups

5.2 Processes Details, Risks, and Responses

5.2.1 Initiation Processes Group

Tables 2 and 3 show the processes that are part of the initiation group, the benefits/success factors, what could go wrong, the consequences and actions to avoid or mitigate risks. Table 2 shows that preparing a charter for an undergraduate final project report or thesis is vital because it helps to attain the benefits described in the second column. The third column shows the risk factors leading to process failure. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 2. Process – Prepare Charter

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risks Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Prepare Charter	<p>Define the scope and goals of the project. Set expectations for all stakeholders. Help the student to stay on track. Provide a framework for assessing the success of the project.</p> <p>In addition to these benefits, a charter can also help identify and mitigate risks and improve communication and collaboration. Enhance the quality of the final project report or thesis.</p>	<p>Unclear Objectives. Lack of Stakeholder Involvement. Inadequate Research. Poorly Defined Timeline. Insufficient Resources. Scope Creep. Ineffective Communication. Inadequate Planning. Methodology Issues. Procrastination. Technical Challenges. Data Quality. Writer's Block. Stress and Burnout.</p>	<p>Start with a well-defined project charter. Communicate effectively. Establish a realistic project timeline. Conduct thorough research. Stay organized.</p>

Table 3 shows the process of identifying stakeholders. The second column shows the benefits of preparing an undergraduate final project report or thesis. Students can identify stakeholders by brainstorming a list of all the individuals and organizations that could be affected by or interested in their project. They can also consult with their supervisor or other faculty members for guidance. Once stakeholders have been identified, students should develop a plan for communicating with them and keeping them updated on the progress of their project. This may involve regular meetings, email updates, or other forms of communication. By identifying and communicating with stakeholders, students can ensure that their final project report or thesis is relevant,

helpful, and high-quality. The third column shows the risk factors. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 3. Process – Identify stakeholders.

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risks factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Identify stakeholders	Identifying stakeholders is essential in preparing an undergraduate final project report or thesis for several reasons: Ensure that the project meets the needs of all stakeholders and secure support and resources for the project. Manage expectations and communication. Gain valuable feedback. Create a network of contacts.	Incomplete Stakeholder Identification. Misunderstanding Stakeholder Needs. Conflicting Stakeholder Interests. Lack of Communication. Failure to Engage Key Stakeholders. Ethical Concerns, Changes in Stakeholder Composition. Overburdening Stakeholders. Lack of Clear Roles and Responsibilities. Resistance and Opposition.	Have a well-defined process. Effective communication strategies. A proactive approach. Regularly update stakeholders. Seek their input when appropriate. Be prepared to adapt project as needed. Consider involving an academic advisor.

5.2.2 Planning Processes Group

Tables 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 show the processes that are part of the planning group, the details and importance, what could go wrong, the consequences and actions to avoid or mitigate issues.

Table 4 shows the process scope planning. The scope of an undergraduate final project report or thesis plays a crucial role in planning, offering several benefits, as listed in the second column. A good scope is crucial for planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. It ensures that research is focused, feasible, and relevant and aids in time management and resource allocation. By defining a clear scope, the stage for a well-structured, high-quality, and impactful project is set to align with the academic and career goals. The third column shows that issues may arise if it's not done carefully. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 4. Process – Scope Planning

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Scope Planning	Clarity and Focus. Feasibility. Time Management. Resource Allocation. Relevance. Quality and Depth of Research. Manageable Workload. Reader Engagement. Alignment with Objectives. Advisors' Guidance. Ethical Considerations	Overambitious Scope. Unclear Objectives. Inadequate Research. Lack of Stakeholder Involvement. Poorly Defined Deliverables. Scope Creep. Insufficient Time and Resource Allocation. Technological Challenges. Poor Risk Management. Inadequate Communication. Lack of clear communication.	Ensuring that the scope is realistic and achievable. Define the purpose, goals, and expected outcomes. Research to understand the project. Collaborate with stakeholders. Clearly outline the deliverables and criteria for success. Implement a change control process. Conduct a realistic assessment of the time and resources. Assess the technical requirements. Identify and document risks. Define communication channels.

Table 5 shows the process of Quality planning. The second column from the table illustrates the indispensability and benefits of delineating quality requirements in the strategic planning of an undergraduate final project report or thesis for various reasons. Defining quality requirements when planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis is crucial for ensuring the work's quality, professionalism, and credibility. It provides a framework for maintaining consistency, minimizing errors, and meeting academic standards. Adhering to these requirements enhances the research's overall quality and impact, benefiting the academic journey and future career prospects. The third column illustrates various potential challenges associated with preparing a scope for an undergraduate final project report or thesis and the common pitfalls to be mindful of. The fourth column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 5. Process – Quality Planning

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Quality Planning	Clarity and Expectations, Quality Assurance, Alignment with Academic Standards, Professionalism, Objective Evaluation, Consistency, Reduction of Errors, Stakeholder Expectations, Credibility and Impact, Personal and Professional Development, Time, and Resource Management	Scope Too Broad, Lack of Clarity, Scope Creep, Overly Ambitious Goals, Lack of Relevance, Insufficient Research Opportunities, Difficulty in Finding Literature, Inadequate Consultation, Ethical Dilemmas, Inadequate Resources, Revisions and Delays	Carefully plan and define the scope, seek guidance from advisors, and Conduct a thorough literature review. Consider the feasibility, relevance, and objectives. Review and revise the scope.

Table 6 shows the process of Schedule Planning. The second column illustrates the benefits of establishing a robust schedule in planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis and the benefits. The third column presents an overview of challenges and potential issues that may arise when formulating a schedule for planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. The last column shows how to address these potential issues.

Table 6. Process – Schedule Planning

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Schedule Planning	Time Management, Deadline Adherence Task Organization, Resource Allocation, Proactive Problem Solving, Consistency and Productivity, Stress Reduction, Balancing Other Responsibilities, Feedback Incorporation, Revision and Editing, Adequate Rest and Well-Being, Long-Term Planning	Underestimating Time Requirements, Overly Optimistic Planning, Inadequate Flexibility, Scope Creep, Procrastination, Neglecting Revision and Editing, Overloading Other Responsibilities, Lack of Contingency Planning, Burnout, Failure to Seek Guidance, Inconsistent Progress Tracking, Lack of Prioritization	Create a realistic and flexible schedule, regularly update and adjust the schedule, Establish a consistent progress tracking system, and complete your undergraduate final project report or thesis.

Table 7 shows the process of Communication Planning. The second column illustrates effective communication's paramount significance and benefits in planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. The third column illustrates several communication challenges and issues that may arise when planning for an undergraduate final project report or thesis. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 7. Process – Communication Planning

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Communication Planning	Clarity of Objectives, Feedback and Guidance, Problem-Solving, Resource Allocation, Time Management, Ethical Considerations, Collaboration, Adherence to Guidelines, Accountability, Conflict Resolution, Preparation for Defense, Networking and Future Opportunities	Misunderstandings, Lack of Guidance, Inconsistent Feedback, Lack of Transparency, Overdependence on Advisors, Ineffective Collaboration, Unresolved Conflicts, Neglecting Ethical Considerations, Limited Resource Access, Inadequate Time Management, Failure to Adhere to Guidelines, Overloading Advisors, Ineffective Presentation	Establish clear lines of communication. Maintain open, regular, and respectful communication. Seek feedback and address any issues. Effective communication.

Table 8 shows the process of Stakeholder Planning. The second column illustrates the essentiality and benefits of stakeholder definition in planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. The third column illustrates that various challenges and issues accompany the essential task of defining stakeholders in planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 8. Process – Stakeholder Planning

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Stakeholders Planning	Clear Objectives, Expectation Management, Feedback and Guidance, Resource Allocation, Accountability, Ethical Considerations, Collaboration, Conflict Resolution, Communication, Long-Term Impact, Networking and Future Opportunities	Incomplete Stakeholder Identification, Misalignment of Expectations, Overestimation of Stakeholder Involvement, Conflict or Disagreements, Inadequate Resource Contribution, Ethical Dilemmas, Lack of Communication, Scope Creep, Overloading Stakeholders, Loss of Stakeholder Interest	Conduct thorough stakeholder analysis. Engage in effective communication. Manage expectations proactively. Clearly define stakeholder roles and responsibilities. Address conflicts and ethical concerns. Regularly update and involve stakeholders in the project's progress.

Table 9 shows the process of Risk Planning. The second column illustrates the benefits of delineating risks in planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. The third column shows several challenges and issues when defining risks in planning an undergraduate final project report or thesis. Being aware of potential pitfalls is essential to manage and mitigate risks effectively. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 9. Process – Risk Planning

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Risks Planning	Risk Awareness, Risk Mitigation, Time Management, Resource Allocation, Quality Control, Project Confidence, Stakeholder, Communication, Ethical Considerations, Adaptability, Conflict Resolution, Learning Opportunity, Career Development	Incomplete Risk Identification, Overemphasis on Minor Risks, Misclassification of Risks, Failure to Prioritize Risks, Lack of Detailed Mitigation Strategies, Neglecting Ethical Risks, Overreliance on Existing Plans, Ineffective Communication, Neglecting Long-Term Risks, Scope Creep, Inadequate Moni	Conduct thorough risk identification and assessment. Prioritize risks. Develop clear mitigation strategies. Regularly review and update risk management plan. Effective communication and transparency with stakeholders

5.2.3 Execution Processes Group

Tables 10, 11, and 12 show the processes that are part of the execution group, benefits/success factors, what could go wrong, and the consequences and actions to avoid or mitigate issues. Table 10 shows the process of distributing information and managing stakeholders. The second column shows the benefits of distributing information and managing stakeholders when preparing Undergraduate Final Project reports. The third column shows that distributing information and managing stakeholders during the preparation of Undergraduate Final Project reports can be complex, and various challenges may arise. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 10. Process – Distribute information and manage stakeholders

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Distribute information and manage stakeholders.	Communication and Transparency. Feedback and Improvement. Resource Allocation. Risk Management. Accountability. Support and Motivation, Professional Development	Poor Communication, Incomplete or Inaccurate Information, Ineffective Stakeholder Engagement, Unclear Project Objectives, Scope Creep, Problems with Team Collaboration, Technical Issues, Inadequate Risk Management	Establish clear communication channels. Define roles and responsibilities. Regularly update stakeholders. Have a well-defined project plan.

Table 11 shows the process Schedule Management. The second column shows the importance of effective schedule management in preparing Undergraduate Final Project reports. The third column presents various challenges and pitfalls in managing schedules while preparing Undergraduate Final Project reports. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 11. Process – Schedule Management

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Schedule Management	Time Efficiency, Task Prioritization, Quality of Work, Revision and Editing, Stress Reduction, Avoiding Procrastination, Coordination with Advisors and Stakeholders, Professionalism, Learning Time Management Skills, Adaptability	Underestimating Time Requirements, Overloading the Schedule, Unforeseen Delays, Lack of Contingency Planning, Procrastination, Poor Communication with Advisors, Scope Creep, Ignoring Feedback and Revisions, Inadequate Time for Reflection, Health and Well-being	Regularly reassess and adjust your schedule. Communicate effectively with project stakeholders. Practice good time management habits. Flexibility and adaptability

Table 12 shows the process of Quality Management. The second column shows that quality management is crucial to preparing Undergraduate Final Project reports. Quality management is critical when preparing undergraduate final project reports, as it helps develop essential skills, demonstrates academic rigor, and establishes credibility. It sets the stage for students to succeed academically and professionally. The third column shows several challenges and issues that may arise when managing quality while preparing Undergraduate Final Project reports. It is essential to be aware of these potential pitfalls to address them effectively. The last column shows the actions to avoid or mitigate risks.

Table 12. Process – Quality Management

Process	Benefits / Success Factors	Risk Factors	Actions to avoid or mitigate risks
Quality Management	Demonstrates Academic Rigor, Ensures Accuracy and Reliability, Enhances Credibility, Prepares for Future Academic Pursuits, Promotes Accountability, Encourages Continuous Improvement, Prepares for Professional Environments, Facilitates Evaluation	Insufficient Planning, Lack of Clear Objectives, Inadequate Research: Poor Data Collection and Analysis, Plagiarism and Academic Integrity Issues, Ineffective Communication, Limited Faculty Guidance, Technology Issues, Time Management Challenges, Lack of Revision	Provide comprehensive guidance. Clear expectations. Well-defined objectives. Effective communication

5.2.4 Monitoring Processes Group

Monitoring and controlling the planning and execution processes while preparing Undergraduate Final Project reports are crucial aspects of project management. These activities help ensure that the project stays on track, meets its objectives, and is completed successfully. Here are some key reasons why monitoring and control are essential: 1 - Progress Tracking, 2 - Risk Management, 3 - Resource Management, 4 - Quality Assurance, 5 - Adherence to Scope, 6 - Communication and Collaboration, 7 - Decision Making, 8 - Client or Advisor Satisfaction, 9 - Identifying and Addressing Bottlenecks, 10 - Learning and Improvement. Reflecting on the successes and challenges encountered during the project can identify future project improvement areas.

Monitoring and controlling the planning and execution processes are integral to the success of Undergraduate Final Project reports. These processes help maintain project quality, manage resources effectively, and ensure the project stays aligned with its goals and objectives. Regular assessments and adjustments contribute to a more successful and well-executed final project.

5.2.5 Closure Processes Group

Closure or finalization processes are crucial during the preparation of Undergraduate Final Project reports as they mark the formal conclusion of the project and encompass several essential aspects that contribute to the project's overall success. Here are key reasons why closure processes are essential: 1 - Documentation Completion, 2 - Review and Evaluation, 3 - Lessons Learned, 4 - Feedback and Evaluation from Stakeholders, 5 - Formal Presentation or defense, Client or Advisor Satisfaction, 7 - Archiving and Record Keeping, 8 - Ethical Considerations, 9 - Transition to Next Steps and 10 - Celebration and Recognition. Closure processes are integral to the successful completion of Undergraduate Final Project reports. They ensure the project is well-documented and thoroughly evaluated. The closure also allows celebrating achievements and transitioning to the next academic or professional journey phase.

5.3 Digital Process

Records generated in the execution of the processes are uploaded into a database within specific folders. Implementing a digital process can significantly enhance the management of Undergraduate Final Project report preparation. Implementing a digital process improves efficiency and prepares students for a digital work environment, where collaboration and effective use of digital tools are increasingly essential skills. Additionally, it can simplify administrative tasks for faculty members involved in project supervision and Evaluation. The combination of digital thesis management tools with various learning theories, as shown in the literature review, allow professors the creation of engaging and effective learning environment for undergraduate students. This approach facilitates collaboration, promotes independent learning, and empowers students to take ownership of their research process.

6 Discussion of Results

As articulated in the introductory section, the study not only introduced but also delineated a comprehensive process map designed for executing PBL projects in collaboration with local companies within the context of undergraduate thesis preparation. This structured method incorporates project management principles, serving as a dynamic framework to address practical challenges encountered by local companies during the undergraduate thesis preparation phase. The tables listing the risks and actions show that by proactively identifying risks and implementing appropriate actions, students can significantly improve the effectiveness of their final project reports. This proactive approach leads to higher quality research, reduces stress, and fosters a sense of accomplishment. Based on the theoretical background presented in the literature review, final project reports can help students develop higher-order thinking skills like analysis, synthesis, and Evaluation – all crucial for effective problem-solving. Final project reports develop research skills and emphasize how final project reports can equip students with essential research skills like data collection, analysis, and communication. It prepares students for graduate studies or research-intensive careers. It is a valuable assessment tool, allowing students to showcase their learning and understanding of course concepts. The proposed approach recognizes the symbiotic relationship between academic endeavors and real-world problem-solving, aiming to foster a mutually beneficial collaboration between educational institutions and local industry stakeholders. Furthermore, the study elucidates by a charter, showing groups of processes and how applying project management principles enhances the efficacy of the proposed PBL method. The identification of risks and the implementation of actions in the preparation of final project reports can significantly improve their effectiveness. By emphasizing aspects such as scope definition, objective setting, meticulous planning, resource management, and effective communication, the project management framework ensures a systematic and well-organized approach to undergraduate thesis preparation. This not only facilitates the seamless execution of projects but also contributes to developing critical project

management skills among students. The proposed digital process envisions professors as facilitators and guides, orienting students, aiding in project scoping, providing mentorship, and ensuring ethical considerations are upheld. Additionally, professors play a pivotal role in structuring timelines, offering valuable feedback, and overseeing the culmination of the thesis through defence preparation and final submission.

7 Conclusion

Applying the proposed method in preparing the undergraduate thesis report process fills a gap in the literature since no previous work has dealt with this subject. In response to the first question "What are the risks and actions to avoid or mitigate risks in PBL conducted in local companies during undergraduate thesis preparation?" The risks and the actions were presented in tables for each phase and the conclusion is that foreseeing roadblocks and taking preventative measures can significantly elevate the impact of final project reports. This proactive strategy not only yields higher quality research, but also reduces student stress and fosters a sense of accomplishment. In response to the second question "How can professors and students manage undergraduate thesis processes digitally and applying different learning theories?" The results show that by combining a digital management process and applying learning theories, professors can create an engaging and effective learning environment for undergraduate students. This approach facilitates collaboration, promotes independent learning, and empowers students to take ownership of their research process. Managing the undergraduate thesis process requires a structured approach involving professors and students. By following the proposed digital method, professors and students can contribute to a well-structured and successful undergraduate thesis process. Regular communication, early planning, and a focus on feedback and improvement are critical elements in managing the thesis process effectively. The proposed method revealed some crucial results, thus contributing to previous studies on the subject and may help overcome some of the challenges of professors, students, and other professionals looking for quality education. The study was conducted based on the experience and knowledge of professors and students. The present study is believed to augment the knowledge of engineering school professors, students, and coordinators and help use the proposed process. As the Introduction Section explains, several papers have been published addressing PBL use in different domains in recent years. However, no previous study related to identifying risks in undergraduate thesis could be found. Notably, this paper proposes an optimized approach that could be used in any university or teaching organization. This proposed method can guide universities in the traditional teaching process to achieve quality improvement. That helps to impact results, representing considerable teaching gains. The proposed method, enhanced by improved communication, enables any university to increase efficiency in education. This study shows evidence that the quality of the process is affected by several factors, some of which can compromise the reliability of the teaching institution. In this regard, process analysis played a crucial role in understanding and implementing actions to improve it. Scope for future research: This study opened some new research avenues. Opportunities for other case studies are abundant. They could be related to a broader application of risk analysis of undergraduate thesis reports in specific cases, enhancing the current method and reducing the risk of failures.

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